

Building for Diversity in the Humanities and Cultural Studies: The Memorandum of Understanding Group in the NFDI (NFDI4Culture, NFDI4Memory, NFDI4Objects and Text+)

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Our poster will present the collaboration of four NFDI consortia that share thematic and methodological perspectives and interests. The Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) group (Brünger-Weilandt et al. 2020) brings together four consortia: NFDI4Culture, NFDI4Memory, NFDI4Objects, and Text+. They represent the research data management and infrastructural needs of the humanities and cultural studies and offer sustainable improvements to research across their respective disciplines. This collaboration not only benefits the work of each consortium, but also offers a model for further NFDI collaborations.

Research data from the humanities and cultural studies are of particular relevance to scholarship, society and the cultural economy, upholding and providing access to our global cultural heritage. The data are also used for machine learning (e.g. text and data mining), for knowledge representation (knowledge graphs) and in other related fields. Preserving the extensive collections of data that already exist in the humanities and cultural studies (as well as those being constantly created) and making them accessible to researchers requires cross-disciplinary, coordinated and sustainable research data management.

The sustainable storage of data in the humanities and cultural studies ensures their usability not only today but also for future generations of scholars. The four MoU consortia, in line with NFDI's overall aims, are committed to the principle of openness, following the FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016) and adapting the CARE principles (RDA International Indigenous Data Sovereignty Interest Group 2019) to their domains. Respecting FAIR and CARE principles as well as openness poses additional challenges – in our disciplines particularly with regard to issues such as intellectual and cultural property and licenses – and FAIR preservation can only mean “as open as possible”. In addition, the consortia share several disciplinary and methodological perspectives, such as a focus on language, objects and artifacts, as well as performative cultural data.

At the same time, their respective communities face different contexts of (and take different approaches to) data and their collection, analysis and preservation. Their commitment to openness and the mixture of shared and distinct methodologies has enabled an intense collaboration among the four consortia. This collaboration takes place in a community-

supported and dynamic process, in which shared initiatives – whether within the consortias’ work programmes or through working together in the NFDI association – are enabled. In this way, the complementary needs, interests and resources of the MoU consortia can be articulated throughout the NFDI with one voice.

Background: NFDI and the Memorandum of Understanding

Of the 26 discipline- and methods-based consortia in NFDI, four joined forces in a Memorandum of Understanding (Brünger-Weilandt et al. 2020) to jointly address the needs of the humanities and cultural studies and to find organizational and technical solutions to their issues. This interdisciplinarity provides an opportunity to develop overarching offerings and to advance the vision of Open Humanities: for universities and colleges, research institutes, professional associations, GLAM institutions, citizen science and the general public.

The “MoU-Group” has developed in tandem with the NFDI as a whole. Early discussions within the humanities and cultural studies related to forming the NFDI revealed both significant areas of common interest as well as highlighting the differences among the various disciplines of the humanities: research data from the humanities and cultural studies extend across a broad range of disciplines and comprise very different types of data, which vary considerably in terms of quantity, degree of abstraction, dynamism and quality (Brünger-Weilandt et al. 2020). Bringing these diverse disciplinary requirements together in consortia that collaborate intensely is proving to be an exemplary strategy for consortia within the NFDI.

Collaboration: forms and themes

Cooperation among the MoU consortia takes diverse *forms* at different *levels* within NFDI:

- **Topic level:** all four consortia collaborate particularly strongly in the fields of 1) metadata, authority data and terminologies, 2) provenance, 3) rights and ethics, and 4) data literacy;
- **Task and work package level:** there are diverse collaborations among *task areas* on specific measures and tasks;
- **Institutional level:** several co-applicants and participants in the MoU consortia are also *part of other MoU consortia*;
- **Strategic level:** the *leadership of the four consortia* have coordinated public statements, advocacy efforts and consortial strategies;
- **NFDI organizational level:** the consortia are seeking to develop their common efforts within the NFDI association, such as in the *thematic sections and the work on cross-cutting topics* (Glöckner et al. 2019).

The different levels partially overlap, creating synergies on each level.

These forms of collaboration are especially concentrated on a particular set of *themes*.

- **Ensuring data quality** is an area in which the consortia share many interests, as they rely on a common set of data types and forms: ensuring traceability and transparency of *data provenance* is a key example on which the MoU consortia have long aimed to cooperate. At the same time, scholars in the respective fields work on different (analytical) questions, raising issues that the consortia need to address.
- **Expanding the connectivity of data** is central to the aims of all consortia, and pursuing this aim is especially promising across closely related fields. The consortia are pooling their expertise and resources in the development of relevant *authority data, ontologies, persistent identifiers, metadata and knowledge graphs*.
- **Developing accessible key services** relevant to our communities is something that the consortia have been planning for a long time and are now gradually making a reality, such as those related to searching for data or long-term archiving. This requires the development of subject-adequate archiving and publication solutions as well as operating models for the long-term accessibility and reuse of digital material and immaterial cultural assets.
- **Encouraging data literacy** is a core issue in which the humanities consortia have shared interests and concrete plans to work together in developing relevant curricula at various levels of training and education.
- **Responding to ethical and legal issues** – such as data provenance, research ethics, privacy (GDPR), and intellectual property rights and other legal restrictions on data usage – is a strongly overlapping interest of the MoU consortia. They, thus, aim to intensify their exchanges on such issues, like the FAIR and CARE principles, and also to cooperate more closely in the context of the NFDI's section on this topic area.
- **Promoting cultural change** in the respective communities represented by the MoU consortia is a key priority. The need for establishing new disciplinary cultures and trans-institutional practices (e.g. with focus on GLAM-Institutions, non-university research, public administration or academic education) regarding research data has become an increasingly clear necessity in the context of the NFDI.

Our collaboration in the MoU group is a first step towards building a common communication structure for the NFDI consortia in the humanities and cultural studies. The size and diversity of our circle of participants poses particular challenges with regard to organization, communication and opportunity mapping. We aim to provide a testbed for illustrating that the emerging infrastructure components can be used across consortia.

The joint poster of this group will present the goals of the collaboration of the MoU consortia, identifying cross-consortial needs and naming some of the most pressing common issues.

References

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